

A Low-Cost Network Architecture Enabled by SOA-Based Filter-less OADMs and Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing

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Abstract: Enabled by digital subcarrier multiplexing and filter-less architectures based on semiconductor optical amplifiers, our point-to-multipoint scheme can cover distances of up to 350 km with OSNR margins > 9.3 dB in typical BT horseshoe networks. © 2024 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

The evolution of metro-aggregation networks must conciliate two key objectives: coping with the increasing bandwidth demand while keeping capital and operational expenses at a minimum [1]. These networks are constructed in a way that packet data traffic flows between a single Metro node and several Access nodes, in a Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) physical topology. When including protection, the Access nodes are also connected to a second Metro node, which, together with the first one, create a typical horseshoe network topology [2–4]. Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) is a transmission technique where a high-speed data signal is comprised of various lower-speed Digital Subcarriers (DSCs) [5], which fits a P2MP physical topology, allowing a single optical hub at the Metro node to simultaneously communicate with a chain of optical leaf nodes at the Access nodes in a network with a horseshoe topology [2, 4]. This reduces the total number of transceivers and optical fibers when compared with typical point-to-point systems, and directly impacts the overall cost of the network [6]. Nevertheless, increasing the number of leaf nodes along the transmission line does not only result in larger transmission distances, requiring the use of amplifiers to reach the desired power levels, but also in a large number of optical elements that need to be traversed, introducing additional power insertion losses and accumulation of Polarization-Dependent Loss (PDL). Thus, we need to minimize the number of components and ideally make them cost-effective and polarization-independent. With this aim, this paper proposes and analyzes an architecture for modern metro-aggregation networks, which could be enabled both by integrating filter-less Optical Add/Drop-Multiplexers (OADMs) and low-cost Semiconductor Optical Amplifiers (SOAs) in a compact energy-efficient circuit with potential for high-volume production, and by leveraging the flexibility and performance of DSCM-based coherent pluggable transceivers. For the evaluation of the network performance, we have extensively measured and thoroughly characterized P2MP DSCM-powered coherent transceivers, and commercially-available SOAs and couplers/splitters, data from which was utilized to construct accurate numerical models that would replicate in detail the expected behavior of the optical elements. By considering Gaussian-distributed fiber span distances, we generalize the results to provide an understanding of the capabilities of P2MP approaches for metro-access in face of distorting impairments such as attenuation, noise, non-linearities, and PDL.

2. Network Scenario

Fig. 1: (a) Diagram of the evaluated 400 Gb/s P2MP DSCM system over a metro-aggregation application. The **solid line** denotes the downlink, where all 16 DSCs are broadcast to all leaf nodes; whereas the **dashed line** represents the uplink, where a single DSC is uploaded at every leaf node. (b) Infinera's 400 Gb/s coherent DSCM-powered pluggable transceiver. (c) Picture of the SOA used to create the numerical model.

Our analysis focuses on the optical system shown in Fig. 1 (a). The network is composed of 16 leaf nodes in serial configuration connected to a single hub node by means of two parallel fibers: downlink (solid line), and uplink (dashed line). At the hub node, we have placed a DSCM-powered P2MP pluggable transceiver [6] capable of producing and transmitting a 400 Gb/s optical signal consisting of 16×25 Gb/s DSCs, which can be individually detected and processed at the receiver of the remote leaf nodes. The receiver of the 400G pluggable can process up to 16 DSCs that may originate at different leaf nodes, provided the DSCs are within the spec range regarding power variation and distortions. The Access nodes house OADMs, which, as shown in Fig. 2 (a), consist of SOAs and combiners/splitters with suitable coupling/splitting ratios. In our investigation, the ratio has been set to 75:25, where 75% corresponds to the through path and 25%, to the add and drop paths. Regarding the operating conditions of the SOAs, the gain of the amplifiers has been configured so as to ensure a given total output power at the output of the OADM. Following this, in the uplink direction, the optical power levels (i.e., the power per DSC) between the input signal of a given OADM and the added DSC are equalized by adjusting the SOA at the input of the OADM. Since the application of interest is metro-aggregation, the maximum distance of the transmission line (i.e., $d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_{16}$) in our investigation does not exceed 400 km, and each fiber span distance d_i does not exceed 80 km.

3. Filter-less OADM Based on SOA

For metro-aggregation networks, it is imperative to develop and construct a cost-effective and loss-conscious node. Fig. 2 (a) depicts the schematic diagram of the proposed filter-less architecture for the Access nodes. The downlink, depending on the amount of loss that needs to be compensated at the next fiber span, may employ a design with one SOA (G_1) or with two SOAs (G_1 and G_2). The uplink always requires two amplifiers: the first SOA (G_3) is used to equalize the power of added and express DSCs, while the second one (G_4) amplifies the complete signal to reach the desired launch power.

Fig. 2: (a) Schematic diagram of the proposed node architecture. (b) and (c) show the characterization of the SOA in terms of gain and noise figure, respectively, as a function of the pump current driving the amplifier.

To construct a model for the commercially-available SOA, we measured it in detail to obtain the relation of its main parameters (e.g., gain, noise figure, and PDL) as a function of the pump current. In this way, in our numerical analysis, we are able to determine the behavior of the SOA depending on its particular operating conditions. Fig. 2(b-c) show the characterization of the gain and noise figure of the SOA, respectively. Here, we can observe that the peak gain of ~ 17 dB at a pump current of 250 mA corresponds to a noise figure value of 6.5 dB. The measurements also hint at the importance of optimal operating conditions as low pump currents or high input power levels would result in a noticeable degradation in terms of noise performance. Furthermore, while the worst-case PDL induced by the SOA can be up to 0.85 dB in extreme circumstances (i.e., pump current < 20 mA), more typical operating conditions (i.e., pump current > 150 mA) result in PDL values of around 0.25 dB.

4. Simulation Results

To carry out the numerical analysis of the selected transmission line, we upgraded the simulation framework presented in [4] to accurately reflect the impact of the OADMs based on the thorough experimental characterization of the transceivers and SOAs. In our investigation, we have assumed a total launch power value (i.e., power at the output of an OADM) of 0 dBm, and a fiber loss coefficient of 0.25 dB/km; aside from the optical coupling losses, all other losses have been ignored (e.g., due to connectors, splices, etc.). Moreover, the analyses account for the non-linear behavior of the fiber as well as PDL introduced by the SOAs and couplers. In our numerical evaluation, the performance degradation due to non-linearities is represented by an Optical Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (OSNR) penalty compared to the ideal back-to-back scenario. The penalty is drawn from reference non-linear simulations

that make use of the Split-Step Fourier Method to determine the 400G P2MP coherent DSCM transceiver’s performance, depending on the optical power along a fiber segment as a function of the DSCs. The non-linear penalty is therefore considered on a segment-by-segment basis and added at the end of the simulation. Regarding PDL, its impact on the system performance is studied in a similar way: we relate the accumulated PDL to an OSNR penalty based on a reference baseline, which has been determined by simulations of the P2MP transceiver. Finally, to provide a generalized performance analysis and expectations, we define the distances of the fiber segments (i.e., d_1 , d_2 , etc.) according to a Gaussian distribution with a mean of 20 km and a standard deviation of 5 km, which allows us to investigate horseshoe-like networks in the metro-aggregation domain.

Fig. 3: OSNR margin corresponding to Fig. 1 for the (a) downlink and (b) uplink directions.

Summarizing the results of 10,000 simulations, Fig. 3 shows the calculated OSNR margin of the transmission line under analysis (Fig. 1) for both downlink (using only one SOA) and uplink directions, as a function of the total number of OADMs (i.e., leaf nodes) and the transmitted distance. In both cases, we observe that distances in the metro-access ranges can be well served by DSCM-powered transceivers, exhibiting OSNR margins > 9.3 dB after 16 OADMs. The downlink case shows a slight signal degradation along the complete transmission line, which arises from acceptable noise figure levels and negligible impact of non-linearities due to the low launched power per subcarrier (~ 12 dBm, since there are 16 DSCs). For the uplink, the degradation of the OSNR margin quickly increases when combining DSCs using optical couplers. Similar to the downlink scenario, non-linearities do not play a significant role at a total launch power of 0 dBm; instead, PDL introduces noticeable penalties (> 1 dB in terms of OSNR margin). This can be easily explained by the structure of an OADM as shown in Fig. 2(a): the uplink path requires an additional amplifier to fulfill the power equalization and launch power requirements; this causes the signal to traverse twice as many SOAs along the transmission line compared to the downlink path. Nevertheless, our results show that the system exhibits reasonable performance margins to ensure robustness in the distance range of 350 km, while simultaneously connecting up to 16 leaf nodes.

5. Conclusions

We investigated the performance of P2MP coherent DSCM transceivers in a P2MP configuration over a network with horseshoe topology, which considers filter-less OADMs to add /drop DSCs at the leaf nodes, with SOAs to equalize and adjust the optical power levels of the DSCs. Our numerical analyses demonstrate that by limiting the total launch power of the DSCM signal to 0 dBm, non-linear effects are negligible. PDL, on the other hand, plays a more prominent role, since the chain of leaf nodes in filter-less metro-aggregation networks can include a considerable number of elements, causing PDL to accumulate. Nevertheless, our investigation shows that 400G P2MP DSCM transceivers are capable of performing with robust enough OSNR margins in networks with horseshoe topologies in the metro-aggregation distance range of 350 km.

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